

Increasing the Accuracy of Tree-Ring Data Processing to Improve Models for Reconstructing Climate

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Abstract

Tree-ring data is commonly used to reconstruct past climate conditions. In many trees, a distinct ring is added to the tree's width each year of a tree's lifespan, and the widths of individual rings vary depending on the environment in which a tree lives. With ring widths corresponding to specific years, researchers can correlate tree-ring data with climate variables. To process tree-ring data, two cores are typically extracted from each tree, and then all cores are combined before analysis. However, more or less than two cores are commonly extracted for some trees. This has the effect of adding sampling bias to the data. In this paper, we explore the correlation of tree cores with climate and propose alternatives to tree-ring processing that would reduce sampling bias. Our investigation of data from the International Tree-Ring Data Bank found that most cores from the same tree are highly correlated, but not exclusively so. About 12% of trees had weak ($r < 0.4$) correlation. Further, these weakly correlated trees produced a different distribution of correlations with a climate variable. We then collected 45 tree cores from Virginia pines (*Pinus virginiana*) in Elon University Forest, North Carolina, to explore alternatives to tree-ring processing. By combining the tree cores from each tree early in the processing pipeline, we reduce potential sampling issues where some trees had more or less than two cores per tree. The analyses also showed that this method could provide further benefits by removing discontinuities in the processing stages.

Key Words: Tree rings, Correlation analysis, Climate reconstruction, Smoothing splines

1. Introduction

The study of dendrochronology utilizes patterns of tree-ring widths to reconstruct past climate conditions and predict future climate trends [10]. During each year of a typical tree's lifespan, a distinct ring is added to the tree's width. The width of an individual ring varies depending on the local environment in which a tree lives [23]. Larger tree-ring widths indicate a year of more favorable climatic conditions for tree growth (warmer, wetter seasons), while a narrower width is indicative of a year with more unfavorable growing conditions (excessively dry and cold seasons) [1]. In dendrochronology, the ring width measurements of individual trees from the same plot of land are commonly combined to form a sequence that correlates with local climate data [19]. This correlation is then used to extrapolate climate conditions for the geographical site back to time periods that pre-date precise climate measurements [9]. Models created from tree rings can inform about how trees responded to past climate conditions, which can then imply responses to future changes in climate.

There are several methods for processing tree-ring measurements that depend on the context that the data will be used. One of the most common approaches for processing tree-ring data has been in use for several decades [7]. In standard practice, two pencil-width tree cores are extracted from opposite sides of a tree, and these pairs of cores are taken from a sample of trees in the given area (e.g., 20 trees may be sampled yielding 40 tree cores) [6]. Because each tree ring corresponds to a particular year, a simple bivariate dataset can be constructed. Once ring widths are measured from each core, a cubic smoothing spline is applied to each tree core [7]. The smoothing spline notation used in dendrochronology [7, 18] seeks to obtain the function $g(x)$ that minimizes

$$2p \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (g(x_i) - y_i)^2 + \int_{x_0}^{x_{n-1}} (g^{(2)}(x))^2 dx,$$

where p is the smoothing parameter, x_i is the year, and y_i is the raw tree-ring width. Per [6] and [7], a target frequency for each core is chosen; for this report, we follow the standard recommendation of choosing a frequency that corresponds to $67\%n$, or two-thirds of the series length. This target frequency, f , is used to determine the smoothing parameter, p , according to the formula [18]

$$u(f) = \frac{\left(\frac{p}{6}\right) \cos 2\pi f + \left(\frac{p}{3}\right)}{\cos^2 2\pi f + \left(\left(\frac{p}{6}\right) - 2\right) \cos 2\pi f + \left(\left(\frac{p}{3}\right) + 1\right)},$$

where $u(f)$ is the amplitude of sequence. The goal is to choose the smoothing parameter that reduces $u(f)$ by 50% [7, 18]. After the smoothing spline is fit, each sequence is standardized. There are a few approaches to standardization in dendrochronology, but we will focus on only one in this paper. This standardization involves dividing the raw ring widths by the spline fits for each year [6]. Finally, these standardized sequences are averaged together, and then the correlation between the final sequence and climate variable(s) is found [6].

The method outlined previously (published in the early 1980s) was quickly adopted in dendrochronology and revolutionized the field. Variations of the approach are used in different contexts (many examples can be found in [6]). Recently, studies have proposed either new methods for processing tree-ring data (e.g., Bayesian inference from [21]) or updates to the existing approach (e.g., accounting for end-point effects in smoothing splines from [4]).

This paper investigates the potential bias that can arise in practical tree core collection settings. As mentioned, typically two tree cores are collected from each tree. However, there are occasions where either one or three or more cores are extracted from some trees. This deviation from standard practice occurs for different, usually justified reasons. For example, more than two cores may be extracted due to the position of the tree on a slope or the preference of the researcher. Regardless of the reason, when a different number of cores is taken from each tree in a dataset, the uneven sampling may impact the tree-ring processing stage [12]. Statistically, measurements from trees that are more heavily sampled should have a larger effect on the final model than trees with fewer cores.

This paper explores the tree-ring sampling process from two angles. First, using several publicly available tree-ring datasets, we show that there can be much variability between two cores of the same tree. The distribution of this “internal” correlation could inform how tree rings are combined during the processing stages. We further explore the correlation between precipitation and tree cores with high internal correlation and low internal correlation.

The second area of our work acknowledges that the combination of tree cores could occur at multiple points in the tree-ring processing steps. Using data collected from Elon University Forest (EUF), we compare the standard practice (smoothing spline, standardization, averaging, correlation against climate variables) against a design that balances the sample by tree. This approach combines tree-rings from the same tree before applying smoothing splines, which results in only one standardized sequence per tree. We then show how the choice of when cores are combined create noticeable differences in the intermediate sequences that are produced. The disparities observed between these approaches will prompt further investigations into how tree-ring processing could impact the accuracy of climate reconstructions.

2. Data and Methods

2.1 Data Collection

2.1.1 Internal Correlation and Climate Data

For the internal correlation analysis, data were extracted from the International Tree-Ring Data Bank (ITRDB), which is one of the largest collections of tree-ring data in the world [15]. To limit the variability among different tree species, only one species of tree was used for analysis, the Eastern White Oak (*Quercus alba*). To properly study internal correlation of trees, datasets needed to have primarily two cores extracted per tree. Data were drawn from the eastern half of the United States to additionally limit regional variability. Table 1 lists the datasets used from the ITRDB, which resulted in 232 tree cores from 116 trees for the analysis dataset.

Table 1: Tree-Ring Datasets from the International Tree-Ring Data Bank (ITRDB) Used for Analyses

<i>Dataset ID</i>	<i>State</i>	<i>Dataset Date</i>	<i>No. of Cores</i>	<i>No. of Trees</i>	<i>No. of Cores Removed*</i>	<i>Reference</i>
IA037	Iowa	2021	22	11	0	[11]
IL028	Illinois	2020	12	6	1	[2]
IN019	Indiana	2017	20	10	0	[14]
MO078	Missouri	2020	80	40	3	[22]
NC023	North Carolina	2012	22	11	5	[17]
NY016	New York	2013	28	14	6	[16]
OH007	Ohio	2018	36	18	4	[13]
WI019	Wisconsin	2021	12	6	0	[11]
Total			232	116	19	

* Some cores were removed that were either not part of a pair or were part of a triplicate. Analysis focused on pairs of two cores. These removed cores are not included in the total number of cores listed under “No. of Cores.”

When correlating with climate data, two negatively correlated tree cores from Iowa were removed, leaving 114 trees with positively correlated cores. Climate data was downloaded from the Oregon State University’s PRISM Climate Group database [20]. For each location associated with the tree-ring datasets, annual precipitation data was retrieved from 1985 to 2022.

Three data subsets were analyzed. The first included all 116 trees. The second restricted the data to only trees with strong internal correlation ($r > 0.8$), which included 30 trees. The third looked at only trees with weak ($r < 0.4$) but positive internal correlation, which included 12 trees.

2.1.2 Elon University Forest Data

For the tree-ring processing analysis, forty-five cores were collected from twenty Virginia pine (*Pinus virginiana*) trees located within Elon University Forest (EUF), Elon, North Carolina. The Virginia pine trees in EUF were second-growth wood that formed after the abandonment of farmland. These trees were generally the same age and approximately the same diameter, providing an ideal set of conditions for ring-width analysis. Collecting data from EUF allowed for a specific number of cores to be taken from each tree. For one tree, a single core was taken, and for four trees, three cores were extracted. Because the samples were collected in close proximity to each other and were from similar trees, collecting data from EUF could strengthen climate signals that ring-width measurements show when processed [5].

Virginia pine produces nonporous wood which is ideal for extraction and analysis [8]. As cores were extracted, a record of each sampled tree’s location was maintained. Following standard dendrochronology protocol, any geographic anomalies, indications of tree stress (damaged bark, dead branches, etc.), and whether needles were present was recorded [24]. Tree cores were collected

at 1.4m above the ground, called diameter breast height, which is the standard height at which tree cores are sampled [12].

Extracted tree cores were dried at room temperature and mounted to a flat surface using wood glue. Cores were sanded to enhance the visibility of the rings [8]. Trees like Virginia pine grow what is called “early wood” in the first part of the growing season and “late wood” towards the end of the growing season [8]. Early wood is generally lighter colored and more porous while latewood tends to be darker and denser. This transition in color provides a clear representation of one year of wood accumulation on a tree, which can be measured accurately with calipers once the core is sanded. After cores were prepared for measurement, calipers were used to determine the length of each annual ring.

2.2 Statistical Analyses

The EUF tree-ring data was recorded and stored in Microsoft Excel. All analyses were performed in the statistical software R (version 4.3.2). The data and scripts can be found at in a Github repository at https://github.com/breutinger/JSM_Proceedings.git. The R packages dplyr [25] and dplR [3] were used for some tree-ring processing steps.

For the 116 trees from the ITRDB datasets, the correlation was computed between the two cores of each tree, termed “internal correlation” in this report. The distribution of these correlations was analyzed to provide insight into the variability of tree-ring widths within a tree. The climate data were merged with the tree-ring data for each site using R. The correlation of each individual core with climate was computed for any year in which there was both climate observations and tree-ring data (i.e., complete pair-wise computation).

Using the EUF data, the tree-ring processing analysis compared two strategies, which vary when core measurements were combined in the processing stages. The first method follows a simple version of the standard tree-ring processing protocol outlined in Section 1. A cubic smoothing spline was applied to each tree core in the dataset, and the smoothing parameter was determined for each core using the 67%*n* criterion detailed in [6]. The spline fits were then averaged to form a “final” sequence. Note: the standardization phase was not included. The goal of the study was to focus on the order of when measurements were combined, so only the first steps of the typical tree-ring process were used.

The second method included an extra processing step to balance the datasets by tree. The tree cores from a given tree were first averaged together. If the cores differed in length (i.e., one tree core included more years than the other), then the values from the longer core were substituted for the average over those years where no overlap occurred. Then, for each tree’s averaged core data, the cubic smoothing spline was applied using the 67%*n* criterion. The two methods were compared visually through graphs.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Internal Correlation of Trees

Because common tree-ring analyses rely on multiple cores per tree, it is instructive to better understand how those cores related to each other. In this report, the correlation between two cores from the same tree is termed “internal correlation.” The internal correlation was computed for each pair of cores from the 116 trees from the ITRDB. The resulting distribution (Figure 1) was left skewed, with most correlations being moderately to strongly positively correlated. Half of the cores had a correlation of 0.72 or greater, with 25.9% (*n*=30 trees) having a strong correlation over 0.80. This finding supports the common idea that two cores from the same tree should be positively correlated. However, this was not exclusively true. There were 14 trees (12.1%) that had a weak internal correlation ($r < 0.4$) between their two cores, with two trees having a negative correlation. Both of the slightly negatively correlated trees were from the Iowa dataset.

Figure 1: Distribution of correlations between pairs of tree cores taken from 116 trees in the eastern half of the United States. Data from the International Tree-Ring Data Bank [2, 11, 13, 14, 16, 17, 22].

Because a non-negligible portion of the sample had weak internal correlation (12.1%), the sample was split between weak and strong internal correlation to study how those cores correlated with a climate variable. When the data was restricted to only those cores with a relatively high internal correlation ($r > 0.80$), the distribution of the correlations with precipitation was also left skewed (Figure 2) with a median of 0.231. There were negatively correlated sequences (minimum = -0.201), but the majority were positive with a maximum correlation of 0.485.

Figure 2: Distribution of correlations between tree cores and annual precipitation taken from 30 trees in the eastern half of the United States. The 30 pairs of cores were all pairs that showed high correlation between the cores ($r > 0$) in the full dataset of 116 trees. Tree-ring data from the International Tree-Ring Data Bank [2, 11, 13, 14, 16, 17, 22]. Climate data from PRISM [20].

The distribution shown in Figure 2 contrasts with the distribution of correlations of precipitation against the tree cores with weak internal correlation ($r < 0.4$, Figure 3). Though the sample size was small ($n = 12$ pairs of cores), the median correlation was lower at 0.149. However, the minimum was larger (-0.109 compared with -0.201 from the high internal correlations). Though more data would strengthen this analysis, the results from this study seem to suggest that tree cores with weak internal correlation tend to be less correlated with precipitation in general. This could suggest a pre-screening stage depending on the focus of the tree-ring analysis.

Figure 3: Distribution of correlations between tree cores and annual precipitation taken from 12 trees in the eastern half of the United States. The 12 pairs of cores were all pairs that showed relatively low but positive correlation between the cores ($r < 0.40$) in the full dataset of 116 trees. Tree-ring data from the International Tree-Ring Data Bank [2, 11, 13, 14, 16, 17, 22]. Climate data from PRISM [20].

3.2 EUF Data Analysis

The internal correlation analysis showed that two cores from the same tree are likely to be highly correlated, but not exclusively. The trees from EUF further illustrated that two cores from a tree are not always consistent with each other. For tree 8-2 (Figure 4) the correlation between the east and west cores was 0.33. In this set of cores, one core had much wider widths (ranging from 4 to over 8mm) than the other (around 2mm) for the years around 1960. Other notable differences occur throughout the sequence, notably in the early 1990s when the tree cores show opposite trends. As mentioned earlier, cores from the same tree do not always contain the same number of years. This is evident in tree 8-2 (Figure 4), where one core dated back to the 1930s, but the other only dated back to the 1950s.

The difference in core lengths is typically not directly addressed in tree-ring processing. The typical process involves having a smoothing spline applied to each core, the sequence being standardized, and the standardized sequences then averaged to produce the final sequence. Because each core is processed separately until the final averaging, all years for each core are maintained.

Figure 4: Raw tree-ring measurements of the west (W) (black line) and east (E) (gray line) cores taken from tree 8-2 in EUF.

From a statistical viewpoint, each tree should be represented equally in a dataset. Any given tree should not have different influence in the final sequence than any other tree. This condition is met if the recommendation of two cores per tree is followed. However, it is not uncommon for more than two cores to be collected from a tree, or to have only one core for a tree. In standard tree-ring processing, each core is given equal weight in the final sequence, not each tree. If one tree has three cores but the others only have two, then the former tree will have slightly more influence in the final sequence. Though the magnitude of this bias is a focus for future studies, our current study considered a tree-ring processing alternative.

Instead of processing each core separately until the final averaging, we began the core processing by combining all cores from the same tree. For each tree, we took the average of the raw ring widths for each year. If only one core's ring width was present for a given year (e.g., tree 8-2 from the later 1930s to the 1950s, Figure 4), then that ring width was substituted for the average. During years for which multiple cores contained data, this averaging could better capture underlying climate patterns for the tree. Sharp transitions occurred when moving from years with multiple cores to years with only one core (Figure 5, gray line). Figure 5 shows how this manifested for tree 8-2 in the EUF data. Only one core contributed ring widths until the late 1950s, when a second core also had data. A sharp increase was observed where this transition occurred. However, following the rest of the standard tree-ring processing protocol, a smoothing spline would then be applied, thus smoothing over this transition (Figure 5, black line).

Figure 5: Cubic smoothing spline (black line) created from the average (gray line) of the east (E) and west (W) cores of tree 8-2 in EUF.

By averaging the cores for each tree, over or under sampling bias resulting from a different number of cores per tree would be reduced. This approach could balance the data across trees more evenly and potentially create a more accurate final sequence. This processing alternative also could carry an additional benefit of smoothing many discontinuities before the final averaging stage. Figure 6 shows a simplified example of this. The black, smooth line is the result of applying a smoothing spline to the averaged cores for tree 8-2 (also seen in the black line in Figure 5). The gray line in Figure 6 follows a condensed version of the standard processing approach. Each core had a separate smoothing spline applied, and then those splines were averaged (note: we did not include the standardization stage to simplify the results; however, the standardization would not change the overall outcome). Because the two smoothing splines had different lengths, a discontinuity in the final sequence occurs where the sequence transitions from including only one spline to including two. This is a similar pattern to what was observed when averaging the raw width (Figure 5, gray line). However, the raw width discontinuity was smoothed by the smoothing spline, thus likely reducing its impact on the final sequence.

Conclusions

Given the importance of tree rings to reconstructing climate conditions, we investigated two aspects of tree-ring data and their processing. The internal correlation of trees, i.e., the correlation of two cores from the same tree, were analysed from publicly available tree-ring data. Most trees had strong internal correlation, but a non-negligible portion (12.4%) had weakly correlated tree cores. The weakly correlated cores produced a different distribution when correlated with climate, which may suggest that these cores may need to be removed during processing to produce better climate reconstructions. Second, we collected data from Elon University Forest to investigate the influence of uneven sampling from trees. Two methods were used to process tree-ring measurements from the east and west cores of tree 8-2. The first is a commonly employed approach which involved the processing of each core separately until the final averaging is performed, while in the second, core processing began by combining all cores from the same tree. Strong discontinuities occurred in the first method. Additionally, the first method weighted the sample by each core, not each tree. The second method weighted the sample by tree, thus reducing the uneven sampling bias. Future research could quantify this bias and the difference between the two methods.

Figure 6: Spline of the average measurements (black line) plotted against the average of splines (gray line) using the W and E cores of tree 8-2 in EUF.

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